

LIBRARY SCIENCE EDUCATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP: A STRATEGIC NEED FOR NIGERIA'S SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Emmanuel Chukwuma Okorie

Library Science Unit, Institute of Education Delta State University, Abraka.

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Abstract: The study was on Entrepreneurship Education for Librarians and Library Science Students: A Need for Tertiary Institutions for Sustainable Development of Nigeria. It adopted the descriptive survey design. Questionnaire was the instrument used to collect data with three research questions. The population included 110 (Librarians including lecturers in library science) from four universities in South-South Nigeria namely University of Benin, Edo state. Delta State University Abraka, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State and Federal University of Petroleum Warri, Delta State. 100% return were achieved. Data collected were analyzed using mean scores and acceptance level was at 2.50. The study among other things revealed that Entrepreneurship Education is relevant for Librarians and Library Science students, for national development. It was recommended among others that the National Universities Commission (NUC) should force the universities that are yet to adopt Entrepreneurship education programs to do so, not only on paper but also in practice.

Key Words: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship Education, Librarians, Tertiary Institutions, Sustainable Development

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is the willingness and ability of an individual to seek out investments and be able to establish and run an enterprise successfully based on identifiable opportunities (Kayode, 2006). It is also viewed as equipping learners with skills, knowledge, and disposition that can help them develop or implement innovative social or business plans. (Oribhabor and Okonta, 2011) defined education as a process of inculcating and equipping the individuals with desirable knowledge, right attitudes, values, skills, capabilities and competences necessary for him/her to realize his/her potentials in the advancement of his/her society. Education is also viewed as a veritable weapon against ignorance, poverty, disease, superstition, squalor and backwardness (Mgbor and Mgbor, 2011). Entrepreneurship Education therefore is the process of providing individuals with the ability to recognize business opportunities, and the insight, self-esteem, knowledge and skills to act on them.

It is all about transforming an idea into reality (Collin and Jack 2004, Akinseinde, 2011, Obaro, 2023). Entrepreneurship education makes human to be responsive to their personal, families, national needs and aspirations (Ighalo, 2001 Obaro, 2022).

Develop means a change into a more advanced form. To sustain means to keep something in existence. Something that has been there before, that is, something that has been in existence. In the views of Okagbare (2011) Development is the transformation of the socio- economic structures like libraries. Libraries are store houses of knowledge which organize and disseminate information for users (Obaro,2021). Librarians are people who process and organize information. They also care for the information resources in the libraries (Obaro, 2023). And because information is power, for any nation to have sustainable development and global relevance, its information house like libraries must be harnessed. The library science students pass through this developmental process, and so should be harnessed timely. Keeping these socio-economic structures in existence is sustainable development. Therefore, the real national development involves a structural transformation of the economy, society, politics, and culture that permits a re-direction of science and technology. This can be seen in entrepreneurship education. Sustainable development then refers to meeting society's need for effective workers which will help to build a great and dynamic economy. It is also giving people knowledge and skills for lifelong learning to help them find new solutions to their environmental, economic and social issues.

Statement of Problem

There have been several entrepreneurial efforts made all over the world for sustainable development. Kifordu (2014) reports that several countries like Malaysia, Indonesia, Indiaetcetera developed their economies through the effective recognition and application of entrepreneurship education, because of the roles it plays in creating employment, capacity building, growth and development. In Czech Republic, entrepreneurship education has been introduced in the school curriculum. In England and Wales, enterprise education is integrated as a compulsory element of pupils work related learning in key stage 4 (ages 14-16). The government in England also funded pilot projects to be developed in secondary schools. In Slovenia, entrepreneurship is also a key competence in their development strategy. From the year 2000-2006, Slovenia offered through different government resources the program for entrepreneurship and creativity of youths (Nwadiani, 2011). As far back as 1984, Zimbabwe was involved in entrepreneurship education when it introduced a policy of education with production.

In Nigeria, the government has made efforts from as far back as 2004 to integrate entrepreneurship education into the curriculum of Nigerian universities. The University of Ibadan commenced this innovation in the 2003/2004 session. They now have a centre called "Centre of Entrepreneurship and Innovation". The University of Nigeria Nsukka has a Centre for Entrepreneurship and Development Research (CEDR) which was established in 2010 to promote entrepreneurship culture and mind set, skill acquisition, self-employment, economic independence and self-actualization. The University of Ilorin introduced the Technical Entrepreneurship Centre

(TEC) in the 2008/2009 academic session. The University of Benin also has established the entrepreneurship development centre for the purpose of assisting innovators and inventors to commercialize them and establish contacts with potential business partners

(Babalola, 2011). Similarly, entrepreneurship education has also been introduced into the general studies programme of the Delta State University Abraka. From a pilot study conducted by the researcher, it was observed that some of the entrepreneurial programmes need to be restructured and some new areas especially in the area of librarianship integrated into the programmes, hence this study.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the need for entrepreneurship education for librarians and library science students in tertiary institutions. Specifically, the study will-

- i. Investigate the relevance of entrepreneurship education for librarians and library science students in tertiary institutions.
- ii. Identify the areas for entrepreneurship education for librarians and library science students in tertiary institutions.

Research Questions

The following research questions were postulated for the study.

1. What is the relevance of entrepreneurship education for librarians and library science students in tertiary institutions?
2. What are the areas for entrepreneurship education for librarians and library science students in tertiary institutions?

Brief Literature Review

The relevance of entrepreneurship education cannot be over emphasized Obielumani (2011) and Obaro (2023) noted that the over emphasis placed on formal education and the neglect of non-formal and entrepreneurial education in our education system has brought about national challenges like youth restiveness, militancy, Insurgency, underemployment, unemployment and a skewed national economy.

Entrepreneurship education encourages creativity. Creativity has to do with imaginations, inspirations, originality, ingenuity and resourcefulness (Babalola, 2011). This is because this form of Education will help develop the young minds into thinking of originality than criminality especially now as reported by Babalola (2011) and Obaro (2023) that most of the Nigerian University students have problems with deep understanding, application and adaptation of knowledge.

Similarly, Osakwe (2011) outlined the relevance of entrepreneurship education to sustainable development as:

- Identifying methods that will enhance and manage innovation and creativity in small scale business in an organization.

- Learning the process of evaluating opportunities properly for starting a new venture or expanding an existing one.
- Developing sound business planning skills.
- Gaining work experience and getting adequate practical and theoretical oriented education.
- Reducing unemployment rates after graduation.
- Enabling graduates have a meaningful and fulfilling life and contribute to the development of the nation.

In the same vein, Obielumani (2011) also outlined the following reasons as the relevance of entrepreneurship education.

- It can create jobs through the formation of new enterprise, especially small medium scale enterprise.
- Harnessing resources that might otherwise remain idle, and put them into productive use.
- Encouraging and sustaining economic dynamism that enables an economy to adjust independency and attain status for themselves in the society.

Librarians Areas of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship education has been identified as a veritable means for national development. This is because, it creates a vibrant economy when practiced and so helps in development. Every area of knowledge has its peculiarity so is librarianship. These areas as identified by Obaro (2015), Onyia and Agbawe (2017), Obaro 2023, include editing, publishing, running a cybercafé and business centre, information brokerage, publishing, book binding, data base producer, running a bookshop, and a fee-based library, managing book clubs, and private libraries, book authorship and translations, and some others.

The peculiarity of these areas is that they are embedded into the library science curriculum in tertiary institutions, and so any serious-minded student should do well in them, in this situation where the unemployment and poverty rates are so high in Nigeria. Entrepreneurship is using initiative to transform business concepts into new ventures and this is expected from a library student. Supporting this view Chowdhury (2014) wrote that the 21st century is witnessing a boom in the ICT driven world. Obaro (2017), Obaro (2023) supports this claim by opining that librarianship is not left out.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was used to collect data for the study using questionnaires. The population was made up of 110 librarians and lecturers in librarianship from some selected universities in South-South Nigeria, namely, Delta State University Abraka, Federal University Otuoke Bayelsa State, Federal University of Petroleum Warri (Fulpre)Delta State and University of Benin, Edo State

In Delta University Abraka, all the 12 lecturers who teach librarianship were sampled. 30 professional librarians who work in the library were also chosen, because they are graded as teaching staff. Federal University of Otuoke has 25 librarians, Fulpre has 29 professional librarians, and 12 respondents, who teach librarianship in University

of Benin were also selected for the study making it a population of 110 Librarians. These populations were sampled because they were considered adequate for the study, since they were professional library staff. A four point ratings scale questionnaires were developed by the researcher as instrument for the data collection. The instruments were validated by two librarians and a lecturer in Measurement and Evaluation in the University of Nigeria Nsukka. A test re-test reliability was conducted with 15 librarians in the University of Nigeria Nsukka which yielded a reliability stability of 0.80 which was adjudged reliable. Results were analyzed using mean. Any response from 2.50 was accepted while any response below 2.50 was not accepted.

Analysis of Data

Research Question One

What is the relevance of Entrepreneurship Education for librarians in tertiary Institutions?

Table 1: Results and Mean of the relevance of Entrepreneurship Education for librarians in tertiary institutions.

RELEVANCE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS N=110

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	MEAN	REMARKS
1.	Entrepreneurial education encourages creativity.	70	30	5	5	3.50	Accepted
2.	It helps in developing business skills	80	25	5	-	3.70	Accepted
3.	It helps in gaining working experience	90	15	05	-	3.77	Accepted
4.	It helps in reducing unemployment rates after graduation	85	25	-	-	3.77	Accepted
5.	It helps in job creation	90	20	-	-	3.80	Accepted
6.	It helps in harnessing resources that would have remained idle	70	20	10	10	3.36	Accepted
7.	It helps in putting idle resources/skills to productive use.	75	25	5	5	3.54	Accepted
8.	It encourages economic dynamism	60	30	10	10	3.27	Accepted
	OVER-ALL MEAN						3.59

Research Question Two

What are the areas for entrepreneurship education for librarians in tertiary Institutions?

Table 3: The areas for entrepreneurship education for librarians in tertiary institutions Some entrepreneurial Skills that Librarians can adopt N=110

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	MEAN	REMARKS
1.	ManagementofCybercafé/Business Centres	80	30	-	-	3.73	Accepted
2.	Informationbrokerage consultancy	90	10	-	10	3.64	Accepted
3.	Editing	100	10	-	-	3.91	Accepted
4.	Publishing	100	10	-	-	3.91	Accepted
5.	Websitedesign	110	10	-	-	4.00	Accepted
6.	Runningabookshop	60	10	20	20	3.00	Accepted
7.	Runningafeebased library	70	20	10	10	3.36	Accepted
8.	Database producer/distribution	90	20	-	-	3.82	Accepted
9.	Online shoppingand marketingof books	70	20	10	10	3.36	Accepted
10.	Socialmedianews makers	90	10	-	10	3.64	Accepted
11.	Commercialbookbinding	65	10	15	20	3.09	Accepted
12.	Managementofbookclubs	80	30	-	-	3.73	Accepted
13.	Booksauthorshipandtranslation	70	20	10	10	3.36	Accepted
14.	Managementofprivatelibraries	80	10	10	10	3.45	Accepted
	OVERALLMEAN						3.59

Discussion of Findings

From the data collected, it is evident that entrepreneurship skills are relevant to librarians in institutions of higher learning. The reasons are not far-fetched because, it will help the students in gaining working experience, which will in turn reduce the unemployment rates of graduates after graduation. Similarly, entrepreneurial education encourages creativity and helps in job creation. This notion was supported by Babalola (2011), Obaro (2023) when they opined that Entrepreneurship education encourages creativity. And creativity has to do with imaginations, inspirations, and originality, which will help develop the young minds into thinking of originality than criminality.

Nevertheless, the following entrepreneurship education, identified in the study can be adopted by librarians and libraries. They include: managing cybercafé and business centres, editing, information brokerage, commercial

book binding, database producer, web design, publishing and so on. (Onyia and Agbawe 2017, Obaro 2016, Obaro 2023).

These views were supported by Igbeka (2008), Obaro (2022), when they stated that Nigeria is gradually awakening to the importance of entrepreneurship development for the nation. Chowdhury (2014) also supports this, when he wrote that 21st century is witnessing a boom in the ICT driven world. And Obaro (2016), Obaro (2022), added that librarians are not left out of these investments.

Conclusion

Conclusively, if a nation must be sustained in its development, then entrepreneurship education must be encouraged. The bookish form of education devoid of practical and skill foundation should be amended. Any country unable to develop the skill and knowledge of its youths, harness and utilize them effectively and efficiently in the national economy will be unable to develop anything else. So, entrepreneurship education is a must for tertiary institutions in Nigeria for sustainable development especially for library students.

Recommendations

Nevertheless, for sustainable development in Institutions of higher learning, the following are recommended:

- a. The National Universities Commission (NUC) as a matter of fact, should force the universities that are yet to adopt entrepreneurship education programs to do so, not only on paper but also in practice, or else sanction them.
- b. Entrepreneurship education training should be sustained in the National youth service programme in the nation. Corpers should also be established after their National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) programme.
- c. Also, entrepreneurship education should go beyond the walls of the tertiary institutions and should be adopted as a programme enshrined in the curriculum of primary and secondary schools.
- d. Idogo (2011) has the view that brain development which is needed in entrepreneurship education is greatly influenced by the environment. Therefore, tranquility void of insurgencies, militancy, and hunger should be provided by the government at all levels.
- e. Ajudeonu (2011) also wrote that entrepreneurship education will be a mere dream as long as Nigeria remains a country without stable source of power. On this light, power supply is inevitable for entrepreneurial sustenance. No business can thrive without power supply, and in this 21st century, it is quite disheartening and a very big shame to note that Nigeria is still struggling to have stable power supply.
- f. Finally, public enlightenment campaign, and current awareness services should be adopted to make the populace know about entrepreneurship education. Even in the universities, most undergraduates do not know the essence of entrepreneurship education.

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